

Analysis of Lightning-Induced Effects on Small Electric Aircraft

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Abstract— The evolution of electric propulsion is transforming aviation, making small electric aircraft more viable and sustainable but presenting safety challenges, particularly from lightning strikes. This article presents simulations and analyses of lightning-induced electromagnetic effects on different aircraft structures, focusing on structural vulnerability and protection measures. Using Dassault CST Studio Suite 2023, the study compares aluminum alloy and carbon fiber composites with metallic mesh. The results indicate that lightweight composite structures need extra protection to meet safety standards, providing insights for enhancing electric aircraft robustness against electromagnetic events.

Keywords: Electric Vehicles, Lightning Protection, Composite Airframe, Indirect Effects of Lightning

INTRODUCTION

The evolution of electric propulsion technologies is transforming the aviation sector, increasing industry interest in the feasibility of these technologies, particularly for small electric aircraft [1-2]. These aircraft offer a more sustainable and economical alternative but also present unique challenges regarding safety and resilience to adverse atmospheric phenomena. Among these phenomena, lightning strikes stand out due to their potential to cause severe damage to aircraft structures and systems.

The electromagnetic induction generated by atmospheric discharges can provoke critical failures in essential components, compromising the integrity and safe operation of aircraft [3-4]. With the growing interest in using these aircraft for various applications, it becomes imperative to understand and mitigate the effects of electrical discharges [5].

This article aims to simulate and analyze the effects of induction from lightning strikes on small electric aircraft with different structural configurations, investigating the interaction mechanisms between lightning and internal systems. Aspects such as structural design and its impact on the system susceptibility levels with protection and mitigation measures that can be implemented to ensure operational safety will be addressed. An in-depth understanding of these effects is essential for developing innovative solutions that provide the robustness of electric aircraft against electromagnetic events, thus promoting the reliability and acceptance of this emerging technology in the aviation market.

A. Proposed Test Specimen for Study

The design of a small, fully electric propulsion aircraft presents significant challenges, such as analyzing the effects of lightning-induced current on the wiring adjacent to the fuselage. Fig. 1 illustrates the aircraft adopted for the studies, whose CAD model was obtained from [6]

Fig. 1: Analyzed aircraft geometry.

The simulated model represents a full-scale twin-engine aircraft. This choice was made to study a configuration with electric motors powered by an energy source, such as batteries. Fig. 2 shows the aircraft model, including the routing of the equipment.

Fig. 2: Conceptual electric powertrain.

The choice of this configuration is arbitrary and does not consider other system operational requirements or aspects of airworthiness. It serves as a representation of a potential configuration to be implemented.

Simulations play a crucial role in aeronautics, allowing for evaluating and validating various effects under real-world conditions. With technological advancements, these simulations have become increasingly accurate and reliable.

A. Lightning Parameters

The standard definition for component A, as specified in SAE ARP 5412B, was adopted to apply a lightning-representative waveform. This standard waveform is illustrated Fig. 3.

Fig. 3 - Standardized component A current.

By definition, this component has an amplitude of 200 kA, with a rise time of 6.9 μs and a decay time of 69.0 μs . The purpose of using this component is to assess transients associated with the first return stroke that could affect the systems.

B. Material Composition of the Model

Various materials are currently used in aircraft construction, whether small or large. The weight of these structures is a constant concern for manufacturers due to their impact on the operation and performance of the aircraft.

For this study, two cases representing viable application extremes will be considered. The first is an aircraft with a fuselage made entirely of aluminum alloy, a material traditionally used by major manufacturers. The second case involves a fuselage constructed from carbon fiber composite with resin, a material increasingly implemented in various modern aircraft parts due to its excellent strength and lower weight. The inclusion of an expanded copper foil (ECF), a well-known solution used for protection against direct lightning strikes, was considered in the first case. In contrast, a heavier ECF was assigned to the second case to evaluate its contribution regarding the indirect effects of lightning. The conductivity associated with this heavier ECF was adjusted to obtain a solution that complies with RTCA DO-160G Level 5 qualification for pin injection. This mesh plays a crucial role in dispersing the current. Table 1 provides detailed information on the selected materials. While increasing the density of the ECF layer is a practical way of reducing the sheet resistance in typical Carbon Fiber Reinforced Polymer (CFRP) laminates, other material engineering strategies may be pursued to achieve the design goal.

TABLE I: MATERIAL CHARACTERISTICS

ID	Configuration control		
	Material	Sheet Resistance (m Ω /sq)	Model Conductivity (S/m)
1	Light ECF	4.00	2.5×10^5
2	Heavy ECF*	0.29	3.5×10^6
3	Aluminum**	0.06	1.72×10^7

* Corrected to yield a short circuit current amplitude close to RTCA DO-160G Level 5.

**For reference only

The study does not consider other structural materials inside the airframe. Although these materials may influence the levels of induced current, their selection is determined by design decisions related to the functionality of each system.

C. Simulated Cable Model

The cables and connectors used in these systems should vary according to specific design decisions. In this case, the cross sections of modeled feeder lines (70 mm²) on both the DC and AC sides of the inverter are shown in the simplified diagram displayed in Fig. 5.

Fig. 2 illustrates the 2.5-meter length of the DC cable between the battery pack inside the fuselage up to the inverter in pylon and the 0.8-meter length three-phase AC cable routed from the inverter to the electric propeller.

D. Complete model

All simulations were conducted using the Dassault CST Studio Suite 2023. The numerical model was configured to run with the time-domain Transmission Line Matrix (TLM) solver, employing a maximum spatial discretization of 2.5 cm. Thin panel formalism was applied to all model surfaces to account for low-frequency diffusion, while all solid components were modeled as perfectly conducting bodies. The cables were incorporated into the full-wave simulation using the hybrid Multiconductor Transmission Line (MTL) solver in CST Cable Studio. The boundaries of the problem space were set as perfectly matched layers, positioned 5.0 meters from the aircraft model, as illustrated in Fig. 4. The simulation scenario considered a lightning attachment to the left propeller, with a subsequent detachment at the tail boom.

Fig. 4 : Simulation setup.

To integrate the electromagnetic model with the circuit simulation of the electrical powertrain - including a battery pack, a simplified inverter bridge, and a three-phase motor - we first ran a full s-parameters extraction task and used the acquired results to generate a macro-model with the rational

function approximation post-processing step available in CST Studio. The circuit, presented in Fig. 7, represents the fitted model by the multi-terminal box labeled as the “Coupling Model.”

Fig. 5: Diagram of the simplified system.

Fig. 6 presents the complete circuit model developed for this study. Although this circuit can be simulated in any other spice solver, all simulations were performed in the Design Studio module for convenience. The following circuit parameters were defined: $V_s = +/ -270 V$, $R_s = 5.0 m\Omega$, $L_{s1} = L_{s2} = 100 nH$, $f_{sw} = 20 kHz$, $C_{DC Link} = 132 \mu F$, $R_{DC Link} = 4.0 m\Omega$, $L_{DC Link} = 50 nH$, $C_{s1} = C_{s2} = 1.0 nF$, $R_1 = R_2 = R_3 = 15 m\Omega$, $L_1 = L_2 = L_3 = 0.4 mH$, $E_0 = 114 V$, $f_{load}(rpm) = 770 Hz$, $E_1 = E_0 \times \sqrt{2} \times \sin(2 \times \pi \times f_{load} \times t - 20.8)$, $E_2 = E_0 \times \sqrt{2} \times \sin(2 \times \pi \times f_{load} \times t - 140.8)$, $E_3 = E_0 \times \sqrt{2} \times \sin(2 \times \pi \times f_{load} \times t + 99.2)$.

In this circuit, P1 is an ideal current source, injecting the standardized component A into the channel attached to one of the blades of the left propeller; the ports P2 – P7 are voltage sources applying the pulse width modulation (PWM) signals to the gate terminals of the solid-state switches Q1 – Q6.

Since an actual all-electric or hybrid system will introduce extra complexities, such as the choice of grounding architecture, the use of multi-stage inverters with sophisticated switching schemes, the presence of bulky EMI filters, and the selection of appropriate lightning protection, these aspects should be investigated in future work.

I. SIMULATION RESULTS

A. Full Transient Model Simulation

The results of the simulations demonstrated the levels of induced current in the cables between the boxes representing

the DC source and the motor, during a lightning event. The points of attach and detach of the lightning channel were defined between the left engine propeller and the empennage. Fig. 7 show the waveform of the short-circuit current in the analyzed cables for each ID case from Table I.

Fig. 7: Effect of skin conductivity on short circuit currents at the DC side.

Table III below compares the levels obtained for each case study, considering different fuselage configurations.

TABLE II: SIMULATION RESULTS

ID	Configuration control			Peak Current Isc (A)
	Material	Sheet Resistance (mΩ/sq)	Model Conductivity (S/m)	
1	Light ECF	4.00	2.5×10^5	15000
2	Heavy ECF	0.29	3.5×10^6	1700
3	Aluminum	0.06	1.72×10^7	340

Considerations of the results obtained:

1) Aluminum Fuselage: Traditionally, aluminum alloys are widely used in aircraft surfaces due to their good mechanical strength, fatigue resistance, and adequate conductivity, effectively protecting against lightning-induced effects in internal systems. It is worth mentioning that even systems installed on aluminum airframes could require extra protective measures at the system level to

Fig. 6: Equivalent circuit to compute the current distribution.

achieve full compliance with current airworthiness regulations.

2) Carbon Fuselage: The carbon composite has been increasingly adopted in primary and secondary aircraft structures. However, carbon conductivity is insufficient to protect internal systems from lightning-induced effects adequately. The induced current levels in the cables were three times higher than the upper limit for pin injection defined by the DO-160G Section 22. These results highlight the need to add extra protection to systems so that levels remain within acceptable limits.

3) Conductive Composite Fuselage: This configuration has been proposed as a hypothetical solution, using a material with sufficient conductivity to keep the typical induced current levels within the established DO-160G limits. Currently, no technology on the market offers these conductivity parameters in carbon fiber composites. This fact is a goal for materials companies to develop technology that meets the demands of the aeronautical industries.

B. Validation of the coupling macro-model

Fig. 8 compares the skin model performed by full transient and the same model with the extracted S-parameters.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 8 : Full transient simulation x Extracted S parameter macro-model. (a) CFRP with low conductivity ECF; (b) CFRP with high conductivity ECF and aluminum.

It is possible to notice a minimal divergence in the result, but both represent the observed phenomenon well. The simulation time used differs for each of the simulation strategies, where the circuit simulation after extracting the S-parameters is significantly shorter.

The simulations demonstrate the importance of the skin material conductivity in controlling the lightning-induced transients to which electronic equipment will be subjected. While aluminum offers good protection, the traditional lightweight ECF in carbon structures results in transients up to 10 times higher than the level 5 pin injection qualification. Although the inclusion of additional metallic pathways is still a standard method of protection today, the search for lightweight, highly conductive materials is a promising field for future technological developments.

C. All-Electric System Lightning Susceptibility Model Simulation

To evaluate how those induced lightning transients presented in the section above affect the electrical powertrain operation, those transients were applied superposed to circuit steady state operation, and currents and voltages developed in each circuit interface were presented below. The type of analysis developed in this section will be useful in future studies to support the evaluation of system aspects, such as the grounding scheme and the sizing and placement of adequate lightning protection at the system level. Although we opted for a comparative analysis of the induced lightning transients superimposing the nominal voltages of the system, it is essential to highlight that if the powertrain components cannot handle these voltages, the induced transients would have to be clamped. The evaluation of the superimposed voltages alone would lose meaning. Lightning transient observed in the DC side of the electrical powertrain is shown in Fig. 9 for skin CFRP configurations with light and heavy ECF. This figure's baseline curves indicate the system's normal operation without considering the lightning event induction. It can be observed that the lower conductivity skin equipment on the DC side of the system may be subjected to a voltage transient of up to 6.5 times the nominal voltage; once for the higher conductivity carbon fiber skin, this transient voltage is limited to twice the operational voltage.

(a)

(b)

(b)

Fig. 9 : Induced voltages at the DC side for (a) light ECF; (b) heavy ECF.

Lightning transient effects on each phase of the AC side for light ECF protection and heavy ECF protection are presented in Fig. 10 and Fig. 11, respectively. It can be observed that the overvoltage to which the inverter switches and electric motor will be subjected is almost 5.5 times the nominal voltage operation for the case where the skin structure has only a light ECF protection but can be even higher if the lightning transient peak occurs at the same time the switch is in high position. From the perspective of equipment protection, this is the criteria for surge suppression design. Higher the surge peak and action integral, a more robust suppressor device will be required, resulting in a heavier and bulkier device, also considering aspects of thermal dissipation.

(c)

Fig. 10 : Induced voltages for a light ECF; (a) phase “U”; (b) phase “V”; (c) phase “W”

Managing the levels induced in system wires decreases the aircraft structure resistivity through the heavier ECF presented above. The induced voltages observed at inverter switches and electric motor windings can be temporarily limited to 150% of the operational voltage. An extra analysis is necessary to evaluate if the equipment can withstand this overvoltage transient. Still, it has the potential not to require a surge protector device in power line wires, which may also be required for some high voltage systems due to personal safety system requirements to isolate high voltage potentials from vehicle structure completely.

(a)

(a)

(b)

(c)

Fig. 11 : Induced voltages for a heavy ECF; (a) phase “U”; (b) phase “V”; (c) phase “W”

Considering an electric motor with neutral point isolated from structure (even during a severe lightning event), the AC currents in all AC phases are not affected by the lightning transient as shown in Fig. 12.

Fig. 12 : Alternate currents at the AC side.

Finally, to evaluate the behavior of the AC currents if a dielectric breakdown occurs inside the motor, connecting the neutral node to reference chassis, we replaced the stray capacitance in this node with a current controlled switch having the same parasitic capacitance prior to the lightning event. Fig. 13 shows that a high overcurrent will appear in that phase for the CFRP structured with the light ECF protection probably leading to system protections to activate.

(a)

(b)

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(c)

Fig. 13 : Effect of skin conductivity on the current at each phase after a lightning strike considering a breakdown at the motor.

II. CONCLUSIONS

Integrated electromagnetic simulations considering the electrical system operation are essential to evaluate the expected transients due to lightning in More Electric Aircraft (MEA) or All Electric Aircraft (AEA) design. These analyses support the definition of the grounding scheme, structural and cabling protection, and the size and placement of required voltage clamping devices. In this work, we exemplify the use of this approach to evaluate the voltages and currents developed on both the DC and AC sides of a conceptual electric powertrain. We first ran full-wave electromagnetic simulations to adjust the composite skin material's conductivity to achieve a standardized level of equipment protection, thus constraining the size of additional lightning protection if needed. Concurrently, we performed scattering parameters simulations to generate a macro-model that could later be inserted in the circuit simulation of the electric system. With the complete model in place, we simulated two scenarios to obtain the voltages and currents expected in the system.

The simulations show significant overvoltages simultaneously occurring at both feeders concerning the single-point ground reference when a lightweight composite is considered the only means of transient control. These voltages likely damage or disrupt the functioning of the inverter, requiring additional heavy protection to preserve the circuitry. However, if a composite material with appropriate conductivity is used instead, the observed voltages would drop to a manageable target level. In addition to these analyses, we also evaluated the transients that would appear if a dielectric breakdown occurred during a lightning strike. This final simulation demonstrates the possibility of evaluating the efficiency of lightning protection together with the failure modes of the system.